

Determination of Ferrous Oxide in Chondritic Meteorite

N. R. SEN GUPTA and A. N. CHOWDHURY

Central Chemical Laboratory, Geological Survey of India, Calcutta

Manuscript received 11 April 1977, revised 12 May 1978, accepted 1 August 1978

An analytical procedure for the determination of ferrous oxide in chondritic meteorites have been described in this communication. The procedure is based on the quantitative removal of metallic and sulphide phases by treatment with bromine-anhydrous methanol at room temperature leaving the silicate phase, coexisting in the chondritic meteorites, unattacked. The ferrous oxide in the unattacked silicate phase of the chondritic meteorites is determined by treatment with HF-H₂SO₄ in CO₂-atmosphere at the boiling temperature followed by the dichromate titration using diphenylamine sulphonate indicator.

THE difficulties in the analysis of the chondritic meteorites are due to the special combination usually not encountered in silicate rocks and minerals¹. In the chondritic group of meteorites, the major portions constitutes the silicate phase but these also contain appreciable amount of metallic (5% to 20%) and sulphide phase (about 5%). The constituents Fe, Ni, Co, etc., are distributed in all these phases coexisting in the chondritic meteorites either in free state or in combination. Iron in different valence state can exist in each of these phases.

Several workers^{2,3,4,5} have proposed various analytical procedures for the analysis of the chondritic meteorites but in these procedures there is no provisions for the determination of FeO. The value of FeO is reported from computation from the analytical data for total iron, metallic iron and iron corresponding to the percentage of sulphur.

The FeO values reported by computations are subjected to errors due to the other constituents. Moreover, there is no suitable analytical procedure for the determination of Fe₂O₃ which is reported as FeO although there are evidences that some amount of Fe₂O₃ are present in the chondritic meteorites either as a mineral or due to weathering of meteorite samples⁶.

This communication describes an analytical procedure for the direct determination of FeO in chondritic meteorites which is based on the reaction that a solution of bromine-anhydrous methanol react with metallic and sulphide phases and can quantitatively remove both the phases of the meteorite leaving the silicate phase unattacked. The unattacked material is decomposed with HF-H₂SO₄ at the boiling temperature in CO₂ atmosphere and FeO is determined in the solution by titration with standard dichromate solution using diphenylamine sulphonate as indicator.

Procedure :

0.2 g of the finely powdered meteorite sample (~150 mesh) is weighed in a dry 300 ml quartz conical flask and to it about 5 ml of bromine is added. The mixture is shaken frequently for about an hour at room temperature (about 25°). After completion of the reaction, about 50 ml of anhydrous methanol are added and the mixture is shaken thoroughly, filtered, washed alternatively with methanol and water till free of bromine. Finally the residue is washed with water. The residue is transferred back to the same quartz flask. About 50 ml of freshly boiled water cool to room temperature, 10 ml of (1 : 1) H₂SO₄ and 10 to 15 ml of HF are added to the flask. The flask is heated to boiling in CO₂ atmosphere till all the samples are decomposed. The quartz flask and its contents are cooled to room temperature in CO₂ atmosphere. Then about 2 to 3 g of boric acid is added and the solution is diluted to about 200 ml with distilled water (previously boiled for 15 minutes and then cooled to room temperature). The solution is titrated with standard potassium dichromate (N/20) solution using 1 to 2 ml of H₃PO₄ and about 5 drops of diphenylamine sulphonate solution (0.5%).

Results of determination of FeO in the chondritic meteorites are reported in the table.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF FeO IN CHONDRITIC METEORITES

Name of the chondritic meteorite	% FeO		% Fe ₂ O ₃	
	By proposed method	Reported earlier ⁷	By proposed method	Reported earlier ⁷
1. Desuri	9.90	10.93	0.93	nil
2. Sitathali	12.80	13.27	0.10	nil
3. Rewari	13.86	—	0.15	—
4. Dhalaja	10.30	—	trace	—

TABLE 2—PRECISION STUDY

Name of the chondritic meteorites	% FeO (Average) X	Standard deviation σ	Coefficient of variation
1. Desuri	9.90	0.13	1.35
2. Sitathali	12.80	0.19	1.54

Discussion

Br₂-methanol has been applied for the determination of metallic iron in reduced iron-ores by Kraft *et al*⁹ and Sasuga *et al*¹⁰. It has been observed by us that bromine-methanol reacts with the metallic portion as well as the iron bound to sulphide (present as FeS) of the chondritic meteorites leaving the silicate portion unattacked. The reaction of bromine with metallic and sulphide portion is rapid and complete and the subsequent isolation of bromo-complexes of iron by anhydrous methanol from the unattacked silicate portion, coexisting in chondritic meteorites, is quantitative and thus permits for the accurate determination of ferrous iron in chondritic meteorites. The value of FeO obtained by the proposed method is direct, independent of errors of the other constituents and does not require to make any computations. The determination of FeO permits to the calculation of Fe₂O₃ in the chondritic meteorites which is obtained by subtracting from the total Fe₂O₃ determined in

the silicate phase^s to Fe₂O₃ equivalent to the FeO determined.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Director General, Geological Survey of India, for his kind permission to publish the paper.

References

1. B. MASON, *Meteorites*, Jhon Wiley & Sons., 1962.
2. G. T. PRIOR, *Min. Mag.*, 1913, **17**, 22.
3. H. M. HEY, *Min. Mag.* 1932, **23**, 48.
4. A. J. EASTON and J. F. LOVERING, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta.*, 1963, **27**, 753.
5. E. JAROSEWICH, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta.*, 1966, **30**, 1261.
6. H. C. URBY and H. CRAIG, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta.*, 1953, **4**, 36.
7. M. V. N. MURTY, *Memoirs of the Geological Survey of India*, (Indian Meteorites), 1969, **88**, 48.
8. N. R. SEN GUPTA and A. N. CHOWDHURY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 710.
9. G. KRAFT and J. FISCHER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1963, **197**, 217.
10. H. SASUGA, K. KATO and Y. ASAOKA, *Japan Analyst*, 1970, **19**, 542.